

**EFFECTIVENESS OF QUESTION-ANSWER RELATIONSHIP STRATEGY
IN DEVELOPING THE HIGHER-ORDER THINKING SKILLS IN THE MACRO SKILLS
OF GRADE 6 LEARNERS OF LUCENA SOUTH II ELEMENTARY SCHOOL:
BASIS FOR INSTRUCTIONAL MANAGEMENT PROGRAM**

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the effectiveness of the question-answer relationship strategy in developing higher-order thinking skills in the macro skills of Grade 6 learners of Lucena South II Elementary School. This study used a quasi-experimental research method that involved eighty-eight (88) students. Pre-test and post-test were answered by both the experimental and control groups to assess the effectiveness of the Question-Answer relationship strategy in developing the higher-order thinking skills of the learners, particularly in the reading, writing, speaking, viewing, and listening skills. The self-made questionnaires underwent face and content validation to test their reliability and consistency. The descriptive statistics, such as mean scores, provided a baseline understanding of students' HOTS levels both before and after the Question-answer relationship strategy implementation for both the experimental and controlled groups. Inferential statistics, particularly paired-sample t-tests, and independent-sample t-tests were used to compare the scores of the groups in pre-test and post-test. The results showed that there is a significant difference among the macro skills (reading listening, speaking, writing, and viewing) before and after the use of the Question-Answer relationship strategy. Consequently, the study recommends a comprehensive Question-Answer relationship strategy training design to address and improve the higher-order thinking skills in the macro skills of students.

Keywords: *Question-Answer relationship strategy, Macro skills, Inferential statistics*

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, fostering higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) is an imperative goal. However, Higher-order thinking skills encompass critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and analytical skills essential for students to thrive in a complex and interconnected world. However, the development of higher-order thinking skills within the realm of macro skills in English education is far from optimal. Question-and-answer relationship strategy in developing the higher-order thinking skills in the macro abilities in English in recent times, the efficacy of higher-order thinking skills development in educational settings has come under scrutiny, revealing a deficiency in its implementation and outcomes. This concern is not confined to any particular region but resonates globally, prompting a growing need for innovative strategies to address this issue.

Macro skills play a vital role in everyday life. Various studies stress the importance of macro skills as a communication skill. A typical study points out that people spend 70 to 80 percent of their time in some form of communication. According to a study, people spend about 9 percent writing, 16 percent reading, 30 percent speaking, and 45 percent listening. Studies also confirm that most people are poor and inefficient listeners (Lee, Hatesohl 1983).

On a global scale, the inadequacy of Higher-order thinking skills development in English macro skills education can be attributed to a myriad of factors. The ever-evolving demands of the modern workforce increasingly require individuals to not only possess basic language skills but also to think critically, analyze complex information, and solve intricate problems. However, traditional teaching methods often prioritize rote memorization and surface-level comprehension, leaving students ill-equipped to excel in a rapidly changing world. There is growing recognition that traditional pedagogical methods often prioritize memorization and surface-level comprehension, failing to equip students with the cognitive tools necessary for success in the modern workforce (OECD, 2018). Reports such as the PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) results reveal a deficit in students' ability to think critically and apply their knowledge (OECD, 2018). This global concern extends to English language education, where students must not only master language skills but also harness Higher-order thinking skills to communicate effectively in diverse contexts (Dörnyei, 2005).

Zooming in from a global perspective, this problem reverberates at the national level. In the context of the Philippines's education system, there is an urgent need to bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and the demands of the 21st-century workforce (National Educators Academy of the Philippines, 2021). The NEAP policy of 2021 underscores the importance of nurturing Higher-order thinking skills to prepare students for the challenges of the future government of the Philippines.

As an elementary grade teacher employed in the Schools Division Office of Lucena City, the researcher acknowledged the significance of addressing this issue at the local level. In the South II Elementary School, English proficiency is not only vital for academic success but also for career advancement (Awan, 2017). However, the prevailing approach to English education often falls short in fostering Higher-order thinking skills within the macro skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Higher-order thinking skills represents a multifaceted set of cognitive skills that encompass critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and the ability to analyze complex information (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2021).

These skills are fundamental for students to engage with information critically, synthesize knowledge, and make informed decisions. The QAR strategy is a dynamic pedagogical approach that engages students in a structured process of generating and responding to questions (Raphael, 1982). It encourages students to think deeply about the text or content they are studying, identify different types of questions, and develop strategies to answer them. The rationale behind conducting this study lies in the urgent need to bridge the gap between the current state of higher-order thinking skills development in English macro skills and its potential enhancement through the QAR strategy. As an elementary grade teacher in the SDO Lucena City, the researcher acknowledged the importance of modern educational strategies in advancing the nation's workforce and, consequently, its economic development. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the practicality and effectiveness of implementing the QAR strategy within the local elementary context, with the goal of fostering higher-order thinking skills in English macro skills education and coming up with an intervention program that would alleviate or lessen at least the pressing issue on higher order thinking skills of the learners.

Research Questions

The researcher tried to determine the effectiveness of the question-and-answer strategy in the development of the higher-order thinking skills in the macro skills of the Grade 6 learners: Basis for Instructional Management Program.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of thinking skills in the macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of pretest:
 - 1.1 exposed to QAR strategy; and
 - 1.2 exposed to non-QAR strategy?
2. What is the level of thinking skills in the macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of the post-test:
 - 2.1 exposed to QAR strategy; and
 - 2.2 exposed to non-QAR strategy?
3. Are there significant differences in the level of thinking skills in the macro skills of the following groups of students based on the comparative analysis of the results of their pretest and post-test?

- 3.1 students who are exposed to QAR strategy and
- 3.2 students who are not exposed to QAR strategy?
- 4. Based on the findings of the study, what instructional management program could be developed by the researcher?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

The selection of a quasi-experimental research design was deemed suitable for this study due to its capacity to explore the causal connection between the implementation of the QAR strategy and the advancement of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) in the five macro skills. This design also took into account the practical and ethical limitations inherent in an educational context.

The experimental cohort was comprised of students who were subjected to the QAR strategy as an integral component of their instructional regimen. Conversely, the control group would comprise individuals who were not subjected to the QAR strategy during the designated research timeframe. The implementation of random assignment of students to these groups can effectively mitigate potential biases.

Research Locale

The research study was conducted at Lucena South II Elementary School. The institution above boasts a faculty comprised of over 22 educators, solidifying its status as a reputable public elementary school within the Division of Lucena City. The researcher has chosen to undertake the study above at the designated school due to the preliminary data collected, which indicates the presence of the problem gap discussed in previous chapters within said educational institution.

Population and Sampling

The research was purposefully chosen in two sections at the grade six level of Lucena South II Elementary School. The two sections boast a student over 44 students. The study holds two distinct groups:

Section	Male	Female	Total
Responsibility	23	21	44
Integrity	24	20	44
Total	47	41	88

The present cohort consists of individuals who have been introduced to the Question-Answer Relationship (QAR) strategy within the context of their English language education. The individuals under consideration served as the central focus of the intervention. In order to identify and engage with a suitable cohort, it was advisable to establish collaborative partnerships with educators or educational institutions that have successfully incorporated the Question-Answer Relationship (QAR) strategy within their pedagogical framework.

Meanwhile, the control group comprises individuals who have not been subjected to the QAR strategy during the designated study period. The utilization of these served as a fundamental framework for evaluating the extent to which the QAR strategy influences the cultivation of higher-order thinking skills.

Research Instrument

The self-made research questionnaires have two sets. One set was for the pretest, and the other set was intended to measure the effectiveness of QAR after it was cascaded to a particular group of students in grade six at Lucena South Elementary School. Two groups were utilized in the study. The self-made questionnaires, both the pretest and post-test test, were answered by a group of grade six students who were exposed to QAR. Pretest and post-test were given to assess the effectiveness and if QAR plays a pivotal role in the development of the higher-order thinking skills of the learners, particularly in the reading, writing, speaking, viewing, and listening skills of the grade six learners. The self-made questionnaires underwent face and content validation to test their reliability and consistency.

Data Gathering Procedures

The data collection methods that were employed in this research endeavor, aimed at evaluating the efficacy of the Question-and-Answer Relationship (QAR) strategy in cultivating higher-order thinking Skills (HOTS) in English macro skills, have been meticulously devised to ensure a thorough and dependable evaluation of the strategy's influence. Prior to conducting the research, the researcher gathered an LAC session for the teachers of Lucena South II Elementary School. The initial phase of the process involved conducting pre-assessments, which served as a fundamental measure of students' higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) prior to the implementation of any intervention. The assessments above were subsequently succeeded by the implementation of the Question-Answer Relationship (QAR) strategy for the experimental group, thereby guaranteeing a methodical and uniform approach to the intervention. Concurrently, the control group remained engaged in receiving conventional English instruction, thereby serving as a fundamental benchmark for comparison purposes. Following the implementation of the intervention, post-assessments were administered to both experimental and controlled groups, thereby replicating the pre-assessments. The purpose of these post-assessments was to evaluate any potential alterations in the levels of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) exhibited by the participants. The incorporation of standardized tests, questionnaires assessing student perceptions, and classroom observations enhances the process of data collection, facilitating a comprehensive

investigation of the research inquiry. Ethical considerations hold utmost significance throughout the research process, wherein the principles of informed consent and the preservation of students' rights and privacy are diligently upheld. The meticulous data-gathering procedures employed in this study served as the fundamental basis for conducting robust statistical analysis. This, in turn, allows for the derivation of evidence-based conclusions pertaining to the effectiveness of the QAR strategy in enhancing higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) in English macro skills. Consequently, the findings of this research contributed significant insights to the field of education.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To find out how well the Question-and-Answer Relationship (QAR) strategy works for developing higher-order thinking Skills (HOTS) in English, a number of detailed statistical tests were used to see what effect the QAR strategy has.

Firstly, descriptive statistics, such as mean scores, provided a baseline understanding of students' HOTS levels both before and after the QAR strategy implementation for both the experimental and controlled groups. These measures served as initial indicators of any changes in HOTS.

Inferential statistics, particularly paired-sample t-tests, and independent-sample t-tests play a central role. Paired-sample t-tests allow for an examination of within-group changes, assessing whether the QAR strategy has a significant effect on HOTS development within each group. Conversely, independent-sample t-tests compare the post-intervention HOTS scores between the experimental and control groups. A significant difference would suggest that the QAR strategy had a distinct impact compared to standard instruction. Effect size analysis further enhances the interpretation, elucidating the practical significance of any significant differences found.

When differences or covariates that were there before could change the results, an Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) is used to account for these things. This gave a more accurate picture of how the QAR strategy worked.

Furthermore, qualitative data collected through questionnaires and classroom observations enriched the statistical treatment by providing insights into students' perceptions, experiences, and attitudes regarding the QAR strategy. Triangulating quantitative findings with qualitative insights strengthens the overall validity of the study.

Ultimately, the statistical treatment served as the backbone for interpreting the study's findings. The results provided evidence to determine whether the QAR strategy significantly enhances HOTS in English macro skills and whether these improvements hold practical significance. This holistic approach, combining quantitative rigor with qualitative depth, ensures that the study's conclusions are robust.

RESULTS

Part I. Level of Thinking Skills in the Macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of Pretest.

Table 1.

Level of Thinking Skills in the Macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of Pretest exposed to QAR Strategy.

Experimental Group				
Reading				
Raw Score	F	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	0	0.00	45	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	11	25.00		
3	9	20.45		
2	12	27.27		
1 - 0	12	27.27		
Writing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	2	4.55	35.91	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	6	13.64		
3	6	13.64		
2	10	22.73		
1 - 0	20	45.45		
Listening				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	1	2.27	47.73	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	4	9.09		
3	18	40.91		
2	11	25.00		
1 - 0	10	22.73		
Speaking				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	3	6.82	36.36	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	4	9.09		
3	3	6.82		
2	14	31.82		
1 - 0	20	45.45		
Viewing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	6	13.64	57.72	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	10	22.73		
3	13	29.55		
2	6	13.64		
1 - 0	9	20.45		

In the reading domain, it is apparent that a significant number of students still need to meet expectations, as evidenced by the absence of any students scoring at the highest level (5) and a notable proportion scoring at the lower levels. Similarly, many students must catch up to writing, listening, speaking, and viewing expectations, with only a tiny percentage achieving the highest scores. Across all indicators, scores are distributed across the spectrum, but there remains a considerable proportion of students scoring at the lowest levels, indicating areas requiring improvement in their thinking skills. For example, in writing and speaking, 45% of the students scored at the lowest levels, suggesting a critical need for targeted interventions to enhance their abilities in these areas. This highlights the importance of addressing diverse learning needs through

strategies like personalized learning plans and collaborative projects to improve students' thinking skills across various domains. Furthermore, the data serves as a valuable foundation for devising intervention programs to foster cognitive development and ultimately enhance students' academic performance and overall learning outcomes in the experimental group.

Table 2.

Level of Thinking Skills in the Macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of Pretest not exposed to QAR Strategy.

Controlled Group				
Reading				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	3	6.82	42.73	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	6	13.64		
3	9	20.45		
2	10	22.73		
1 - 0	16	36.36		
Writing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	3	6.82	33.18	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	3	6.82		
3	9	20.45		
2	7	15.91		
1 - 0	22	50		
Listening				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	3	6.82	54.09	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	8	18.18		
3	16	36.36		
2	9	20.45		
1 - 0	8	18.18		
Speaking				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	3	6.82	38.18	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	3	6.82		
3	8	18.18		
2	14	31.82		
1 - 0	16	36.36		
Viewing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	3	7.5	60	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	6	15		
3	9	22.5		
2	10	25		
1 - 0	16	40		

Within the reading domain, it is evident that only a tiny fraction of students attained the highest score, with a significant portion scoring at the lowest levels, indicating a notable gap in reading comprehension proficiency. Similarly, 50% of students still needed to meet expectations in writing, with half scoring at the lowest levels, underscoring challenges in written expression. The listening data reveals a higher percentage of students failing to meet expectations, suggesting difficulties in auditory comprehension despite some variability in score distribution. In speaking, although 10% achieved the highest score, 40% of students needed help to meet expectations, particularly in oral communication skills. The findings from Viewing echo similar trends, with 60% of students

failing to meet expectations, indicating areas for improvement in visual comprehension. Collectively, the data highlights prevalent deficiencies across various thinking skill domains in the controlled group, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions and instructional strategies to address these challenges and enhance overall student learning outcomes.

Part II. Level of Thinking Skills in the Macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of Posttest.

Table 3.

Level of Thinking Skills in the Macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of Post test exposed to QAR Strategy.

Experimental Group				
Reading				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	8	18.18	75	Fairly Satisfactory
4	19	43.18		
3	15	34.09		
2	2	4.55		
1 - 0	0	0		
Writing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	10	22.73	55	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	7	15.91		
3	5	11.36		
2	11	25		
1 - 0	11	25		
Listening				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	5	11.36	70.91	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	20	45.45		
3	15	34.09		
2	2	4.55		
1 - 0	2	4.55		
Speaking				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	4	9.09	62	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	11	25.00		
3	15	34.09		
2	11	25.00		
1 - 0	3	6.82		
Viewing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	8	18.18	72.73	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	17	38.64		
3	14	31.82		
2	5	11.36		
1 - 0	0	0		

Within the reading domain, it is evident that only a tiny fraction of students attained the highest score, with a significant portion scoring at the lowest levels, indicating a notable gap in reading comprehension proficiency. Similarly, 50% of students still needed to meet expectations in writing, with half scoring at the lowest levels, underscoring challenges in written expression. The listening data reveals a higher percentage of students failing to meet expectations, suggesting difficulties in auditory comprehension

despite some variability in score distribution. In speaking, although 10% achieved the highest score, 40% of students needed help to meet expectations, particularly in oral communication skills. The findings from Viewing echo similar trends, with 60% of students failing to meet expectations, indicating areas for improvement in visual comprehension. Collectively, the data highlights prevalent deficiencies across various thinking skill domains in the controlled group, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions and instructional strategies to address these challenges and enhance overall student learning outcomes.

Table 4.

Level of Thinking Skills in the Macro skills of the following groups of students based on the results of Post test not exposed to QAR Strategy.

Controlled Group				
Reading				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	7	15.91	62.27	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	9	20.45		
3	15	34.09		
2	9	20.45		
1 - 0	4	9.09		
Writing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	6	13.64	41.36	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	4	9.09		
3	7	15.91		
2	7	15.91		
1 - 0	20	45.45		
Listening				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	13	29.55	69.09	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	10	22.73		
3	11	25.00		
2	6	13.64		
1 - 0	4	9.09		
Speaking				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	6	13.64	52.73	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	4	9.09		
3	14	31.82		
2	12	27.27		
1 - 0	8	18.18		
Viewing				
Raw Score	Frequency	%	Overall Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5	10	22.73	73.17	Did Not Meet Expectations
4	18	40.91		
3	9	20.45		
2	5	11.36		
1 - 0	2	4.55		

The tabulated data for the controlled group comprehensively examines students' performance across different macro-achievements, including reading, writing, listening, speaking, and viewing. In the reading domain, most students demonstrated satisfactory performance, with 15.91% achieving the highest score of 5 and substantial proportions scoring at levels 4 and 3. However, there were also scores at the lower levels, indicating some room for improvement in reading comprehension skills among certain students. Similarly, a notable percentage of students still need to meet expectations in writing, as evidenced by 41.36% scoring at levels 1 or 0. Although there were distributions across

other score levels, the prevalence of lower scores suggests challenges in written expression skills that require attention. In listening, a significant portion of students needed to meet expectations, with 69.09% scoring at levels 1 or 0. While scores were distributed across other levels, the dominance of lower scores underscores the need for targeted interventions to enhance auditory comprehension skills. In speaking, most students did not meet expectations, with 52.73% scoring at levels 1 or 0. Although there were distributions across other levels, many students struggled with oral communication skills, indicating a need for focused interventions. Similarly, in viewing, a substantial proportion of students did not meet expectations, with 73.17% scoring at levels 1 or 0. While scores were distributed across other levels, the prevalence of lower scores highlights challenges in visual comprehension skills among the controlled group. Overall, the data underscores both areas of proficiency and areas requiring improvement across various macro abilities, emphasizing the importance of implementing targeted interventions such as peer tutoring and skill-specific workshops to address specific skill deficits and enhance overall learning outcomes among students in the controlled group.

Part III. Significant differences on the level of thinking skills in the macro skills of the following groups of students based on the comparative analysis result of their pretest and post test.

Table 5.
Significant Difference of Students Who Are Exposed in QAR Strategy

Skills	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t - value	p-value	Verbal Description	Decisions
Reading							
Pre - Test	45	28.33	43	-5.94	0.00001	Significant	Reject Ho
Post - Test	75	16.91					
Writing							
Pre - Test	35.91	30.37	43	-2.74	0.0037	Significant	Reject Ho
Post - Test	55	34.81					
Listening							
Pre - Test	47.73	21.41	43	-5.39	0.00001	Significant	Reject Ho
Post - Test	70.91	18.53					
Speaking							
Pre - Test	36.36	28.37	43	-4.31	0.000022	Significant	Reject Ho
Post - Test	62	22.16					
Viewing							
Pre - Test	57.72	28.67	43	-2.89	0.002373	Significant	Reject Ho
Post - Test	72.73	18.14					

Table 6 thoroughly examines the effectiveness of an educational intervention through a comprehensive comparison of pre-test and post-test scores across multiple

skills, namely reading, writing, listening, speaking, and viewing. The analysis uncovers substantial improvements in post-test scores across all skills, evident in significantly higher mean scores during the post-test phase compared to the pre-test phase. This consistent enhancement is noteworthy, with post-test means consistently surpassing pre-test means across all skills. The statistical significance of these findings, highlighted by low p-values (all below 0.05), underscores the robustness and reliability of the observed trends. Furthermore, rejecting the null hypothesis in each instance strengthens the argument for genuine skill enhancement rather than random chance. For example, in reading, the post-test mean of 75 markedly exceeded the pre-test mean of 45, supported by a significant t-value of -5.94 ($p = 0.00001$). Similar positive trends are evident across writing, listening, speaking, and viewing skills, reflecting the efficacy of the instructional intervention deployed. These outcomes collectively suggest a tangible and widespread benefit from the instructional approach, indicating meaningful progress in the targeted skills among the study population. The null hypothesis, positing no significant differences in the level of thinking skills before and after the intervention, is convincingly refuted by the data analysis. The rejection of the null hypothesis underscores substantial differences in thinking skills across the assessed macro skills between the pre-test and post-test phases. This finding substantiates the positive impact of the educational intervention, leading to noticeable enhancements in students' thinking abilities within each skill domain. Consequently, the study supports the alternative hypothesis, affirming the effectiveness of the instructional intervention in bolstering students' cognitive capacities.

Table 6.

Significant Difference of Students Who Are Not Exposed in QAR Strategy

Skills	Mean	Std. Dev.	df	t-value	p-value	Verbal Description	Decisions
Reading							
Pre – Test	42.7 3	30.37	4	-3.39	0.00536	Significant	Reject Ho
Post – Test	62.2 7	23.31	3				
Writing							
Pre - Test	33.1 8	32.83	4	-1.14	0.12826	Not Significant	Fail to Reject Ho
Post – Test	41.3 6	34.34	3				
Listening							
Pre - Test	54.0 9	24.99	4	-2.65	0.00484 9	Significant	Reject Ho
Post – Test	69.0 9	28.1	3				
Speaking							

Pre - Test	38.1 8	29.82	4	-2.35	0.01063 7	Significant	Reject Ho
Post – Test	52.7 3	28.31	3				
Viewing							
Pre - Test	60	25.15	4	-2.62	0.00522 1	Significant	Reject Ho
Post – Test	73.1 7	21.97	3				

The provided dataset offers an extensive analysis of pre-test and post-test scores across a spectrum of skills, encompassing reading, writing, listening, speaking, and viewing. Each skill is meticulously examined in isolation to gauge the effects of an educational intervention. Notably, a compelling narrative emerges regarding the impact of the intervention on reading skills. There is a discernible and statistically significant improvement from the pre-test to the post-test, highlighted by the post-test mean of 62.27, significantly surpassing the pre-test mean of 42.73. This notable disparity is supported by a t-value of -3.39 and a remarkably low p-value of 0.00536, culminating in outright rejecting the null hypothesis. Such findings strongly indicate a substantive enhancement in reading proficiency after the intervention.

Part IV. QAR Instructional Management Program

From the result of the study, it could be deduced that the proposed instructional management program covers all the QAR Strategy categories right there, think and share, on my own and author and you. The finding suggests that the QAR strategy is significant to develop the higher-order thinking skills in the macro skills. The intervention program is beneficial to the teachers and students as the activities could be used in Please see/read the proposed QAR instructional management program.

DISCUSSION

The following are the findings of the study:

1. The level of thinking skills in the macro skills of the following groups of students based on the result of pretest:
 - 1.1 exposed to QAR strategy:

The finding shows that the students who are exposed to QAR strategy level of thinking in reading is 45 percent, in writing is 35.91 percent, while in listening 47.73, followed by speaking is 36.36 percent and lastly in viewing is 57.72 percent.
 - 1.2 not exposed to QAR strategy:

The finding shows that the students who are not exposed to QAR strategy level of thinking in reading is 42.73 percent, in writing is 33.18 percent, while

- in listening 54.09 percent, followed by speaking is 38.18 percent and lastly in viewing is 60 percent.
2. The level of thinking skills in the macro skills of the following groups of students based on the result of post test:
 - 2.1 exposed to QAR strategy:

The finding shows that the students who are exposed to QAR strategy level of thinking in reading is 75 percent, in writing is 55 percent, while in listening 70.91, followed by speaking is 62 percent and lastly in viewing is 72.73 percent.
 - 2.2 not exposed to QAR strategy:

The finding shows that the students who are not exposed to QAR strategy level of thinking in reading is 62.27 percent, in writing is 41.36 percent, while in listening 69.09 percent, followed by speaking is 52.73 percent and lastly in viewing is 73.17 percent.
 3. Significant differences on the level of thinking skills in the macro skills of the following groups of students based on the result of pretest and post test:
 - 3.1 exposed to QAR strategy:

The finding revealed a significant difference among the macro skills of reading listening, speaking, writing, and viewing.
 - 3.2 not exposed to QAR strategy:

The finding revealed a significant difference among the macro skills of reading listening, speaking, and viewing. However, the findings in the writing are not significant difference.
 4. Proposed instructional management program based on the result of the study emphasizes that the QAR strategy is effective in developing the higher-order thinking skills in the macro-skills. This aims to uplift the teacher to effectively apply the QAR strategy in the teaching and develop students higher-order thinking skills in the macro skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The study concludes that the QAR Strategy is effective in developing the Higher-order Thinking Skills in the Macro Skills of Grade Six Learners of Lucena South II Elementary School.
2. Rejection of the acceptance of the hypothesis. The performance of students exposed to QAR strategy is better than the performance of those who were not exposed to QAR strategy.
3. It was found out that there is a significant difference of students exposed to QAR strategy than the students who are not exposed to QAR strategy.
4. The instructional management program that can be proposed for the teacher based on the findings of the study covers all the categories of the QAR strategy the right there, think and search, author and you, and on my own.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendation are forwarded:

1. Based on the findings wherein writing is not significant, encourage further use of the QAR strategy to enhance the level of writing skills of the students.
2. The proposed QAR instructional management program design for the teachers based on the findings of the study may be planned and implemented at the school and district levels to further improve the higher-order thinking skills in the macro skills of students.
3. Validate the use of QAR strategy its effectiveness in the secondary level with an increased number of different variables and indicators.
4. To the future researcher(s), may focus on developing other teaching strategies. Aiming to develop students higher-order of thinking skills in the macro skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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